

MACROECONOMIC INDICATORS OF THE EFFICIENCY OF TRANSPORT LOGISTICS SERVICES AND WAYS OF THEIR DETERMINATION

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ABSTRACT

This article provides a macro-level analysis of the efficiency of enterprises providing transport logistics services. The share of enterprises providing transportation and storage services in the national economy is analyzed. Based on the results of the analysis, micro-level indicators representing the efficiency of enterprises providing transportation and storage services are proposed. Based on the volume of transported cargo and the grouping of cargo turnover by types of transport, road transport with a large share was analyzed. The share of small business entities within the enterprises providing transportation and storage services, the estimated value created by them is indicated. The share of this sector in the GDP was also paid attention to, and an indicator representing the efficiency was proposed in this regard.

It is suggested that the macro-level indicators representing the mentioned efficiency be grouped separately in relation to domestic and international freight transportation, which ensures that the efficiency indicator is used at two different levels.

Indicators related to the dynamics of the number of employees and the enterprises and organizations engaged in transportation and storage providing transport logistics services are also presented, which allow forecasting and determining the future perspective in this area.

Keywords: freight, transportation and storage, transport logistic firms, transport logistic services, efficiency indicators.

INTRODUCTION. Business entities constantly strive for higher profits as the final result of their activities. One of the factors that influence the increase in profit is the increase in efficiency. Today, as one of the areas with a high growth trend in our national economy, the importance of analyzing transport logistics services companies, logistics centers and dispatching activities is increasing.

METHODS. The number of enterprises and organizations operating in the field of transportation and storage services is increasing as a result of the opportunities created by the reforms being carried out in our country. This, in turn, is reflected in the national economy. In January-September 2022, 5.2% of the country's GDP belongs to the transportation and storage network. Simplification of the process of establishing an enterprise, reduction of customs and formalization work opened a wide way for the development of this sector. The line diagram presented below represents the dynamics of changes in the number of enterprises and organizations operating in the field of transportation and storage services over the years.

Figure № 1 Dynamics of growth of the number of enterprises and organizations operating in the field of transportation and storage services

Since 2018, it can be seen that the number of enterprises and organizations operating in the field of transportation and storage services is only increasing. As of 2018, the number of enterprises and organizations operating in this field was 13,099, and in 2022, their number increased by 7,118 to 20,217.

Years	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Number	13099	15268	16969	18846	20217
Growth rate	x	116.6	111.1	111.1	107.3

Figure № 2 The number of enterprises and organizations operating in the field of transportation and storage services

The analysis of the number of enterprises in the last 5 years shows that the enterprises operating in this field increased by an average of 10% during this five-year period compared to the previous one. The largest increase compared to the previous year was 116.6 percent in 2019. In 2022, compared to 2021, it increased by 7.3%, which is the lowest growth rate. The overall growth trend has been maintained over the five-year period. This growth trend is also reflected in gross value added. In January-September 2022, 30,006.5 billion soums of gross added value was created in the field of transportation and storage. Compared to 2018, this value has increased by 27.8%. This is explained by the increase in the number of enterprises. Looking at the composition of added value, road transport is the leader with 58.8%. In the months of January-June of this year, almost half of the total volume of goods transported in road transport, 45.5%, was carried out by small business entities. Among these small business entities, the main place is occupied by small enterprises and micro-firms, which make up 30.6%.

Indicators	2018	2019	2020	2021
Freight transported, mln. tons	1 243,0	1 319,8	1 366,7	1 420,2
railroad	68,4	70,1	70,6	72,0
motor *	1 102,2	1 177,7	1 238,2	1 282,0
pipeline	72,4	72,0	57,9	66,2
air, thsd. tons	13,1	10,4	5,3	9,1
Freight turnover, bln. ton-km	71,3	72,6	66,9	74,8
railroad	22,9	23,4	23,6	24,6
motor *	14,6	15,9	16,2	19,1
pipeline	33,6	33,2	26,8	30,8
air, mln. ton-km	123,5	119,0	219,0	303,5

Figure № 3 Freight transportation and freight turnover by transport type

The volume of cargo transported by these enterprises in 2021 was 1,420.2 million tons. 1,282 mln. Tonnage corresponds to the contribution of road transport. Cargo turnover was 74.8 billion ton-km.

RESULTS. It can be seen that the volume of services provided in this network is increasing. This means that the network is working effectively. In order to represent the efficiency of transport logistics services at the macro level, several indicators should be included. We suggest using the following as such indicators:

1. An indicator representing the percentage share of each type of transport in the total volume of transported cargo. In this case, it is possible to monitor the total transported load and the efficiency of each type of transport over the years.
2. The indicator representing the share of each type of transport in the volume of cargo turnover in percentage. It is possible to observe the contribution of each type of transport to the total cargo turnover and the efficiency of its activity over the years.
3. The number of enterprises engaged in transportation and storage and the length of roads in use according to each type of transport is an indicator representing the ratio in the cross-section of years. It is necessary to calculate it separately for those engaged in domestic and international transportation. Indicators for groups such as length of public roads and traffic roads.
4. An indicator representing the share of employees employed in transportation and storage in the total number of jobs.
5. The indicator representing the average share of one enterprise in the total provided transport and storage services.
6. Indicators representing the share of each enterprise and employee in the total transported cargo and cargo turnover.

DISCUSSION. These indicators represent the shares corresponding to the contribution of each enterprise at the macro level. The dynamics of the number of enterprises makes it possible to predict the impact of changes on these indicators. This leads to an increase in the sector's contribution to GDP.

CONCLUSION. Based on the results of the analysis, micro-level indicators representing the efficiency of enterprises providing transportation and storage services are proposed. Based on the volume of transported cargo and the grouping of cargo turnover by types of transport, road transport with a large share was analyzed. The share of small business entities within the enterprises providing transportation and storage services, the estimated value created by them is indicated. The share of this sector in the GDP was also paid attention to, and an indicator representing the efficiency was proposed in this regard. It is suggested that the macro-level indicators representing the mentioned efficiency be grouped separately in relation to domestic and international freight transportation, which ensures that the efficiency indicator is

used at two different levels. Indicators related to the dynamics of the number of employees and the enterprises and organizations engaged in transportation and storage providing transport logistics services are also presented, which allow forecasting and determining the future perspective in this area.

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